

Effect of Dialysis on Coagulation Constants of Ferric Hydroxide Sol

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Bhattacharya *et al.*¹ have proposed a relation between the concentration of the electrolyte and the corresponding time of coagulation by an equation:

$$1/(c-a) = (n/m).t + 1/m$$

where a , m , and n are constants. The theoretical justification of the above equation has been put forward by Ghosh and Gangopadhyay². Yadav and Verma³ reported that the rise in temperature caused a decrease in the values of the constants (a , m , and n). Bhattacharya and Kumar⁴ have studied the influence of dialysis on electrophoretic velocity of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol in the aspect of charge density and ζ -potential. Since the stability of the sol changes on dialysis, these constants obviously will no longer have the same value at all the stages of dialysis, as these are related to the stability of the sol. Thus an attempt has been made to study the effect of dialysis on the above constants, using KCl , KBr , and KI as the coagulating electrolytes.

$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol was prepared and subjected to dialysis. The time of coagulation of the sol at different periods of dialysis was determined according to Bhattacharya and Kumar⁴ and Singh and Bansal⁵. For the calculation of the values of these constants, graphical method, as reported by Singh and Bansal⁶, was employed.

TABLE I

Conc. of the sol = 14.96g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre.

Dialy- sed (days)	Sp. cond. of the sol ($\text{mhos} \times 10^3$)	a (mM/l).			m (mM/l).			n (min^{-1}).		
		KCl.	KBr.	KI.	KCl.	KBr.	KI.	KCl.	KBr.	KI.
7	0.5074	400	800	140	704.20	4167.00	1000.00	664.40	2273.00	4043.00
10	2.5633	100	200	125	142.80	400.00	500.00	92.85	95.87	338.40
13	1.3011	75	100	125	88.02	227.30	277.70	87.44	77.91	148.10
16	0.9460	50	90	125	66.67	190.10	222.22	37.58	140.00	71.11
19	0.5828	50	75	120	38.46	80.06	208.40	50.76	55.08	62.92
22	0.4974	32	60	80	35.97	57.15	133.30	14.52	26.54	33.59

1. *This Journal*, 1951, 28, 179; *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1955, 10, 551.
2. *This Journal*, 1959, 36, 811.
3. *Ibid.*, 1962, 39, 325.
4. *Ibid.*, 1964, 41, 338, 343.
5. *Koll. Z. Polymer.*, 1963, 189, 140.
6. *This Journal*, 1964, 41, 83.

It appears from Table I that the values of the constants a , m , and n decrease with the progress of dialysis of the sol. The values of a , the critical stability concentration, and of m , the concentration of the electrolyte above the critical value to cause instantaneous coagulation, have been found to decrease rapidly in the initial period of dialysis (7 to 13 days), but on further dialysis the fall becomes gradual.

The decrease in the value of a shows that the value of concentration causing no coagulation is reached at a lower concentration on dialysing the sol. The decrease in the values of m indicates that a much smaller quantity of the electrolyte is required on dialysing the sol to cause its instantaneous coagulation. Similarly the decrease in the value of n indicates a greater degree of aggregation on dialysis.

A sol is well known to become increasingly sensitive with progressive dialysis and since a , m , and n are connected with the sensitivity, the values of these constants should decrease with the time of dialysis and this fact has also been confirmed experimentally.

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